

EDUCATION - AN IMPORTANT TOOL FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

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ABSTRACT

According to Pandit Jawaharlal Neheru, "If you educate a man you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family". In various ways, women were not treated properly for the last centuries. Now-a-days, empowerment of women is the most important concerns of 21st century. And in reality women empowerment is still an illusion in practical field. Various factors such as age, family, social status, educational status, economic status, geographical location etc. are responsible for women empowerment. Education is the key for unlocking the golden doors of freedom for all round development. Education is considered to be a fundamental right for all and is considered to be the milestone for women empowerment as it enables them to achieve their goals, can respond their challenges and change their lifestyle. Educated women can play an important role in eradicating poverty and accelerates the development process. The stability, peace and prosperity of a family depends upon the proper education of females. Women have huge amount of unexplored potential which has never been justified. In this paper, the investigators have discussed about the educational status of women, problems faced by women, women empowerment through education, constitutional and legal provisions for women, Governmental initiatives for women empowerment and some valuable suggestions for women empowerment.

Keywords: Education, Important Tool, Women and Empowerment

INTRODUCTION

Empowerment is defined as "The enhancement of assets and capabilities of diverse individuals and groups to engage, influence and hold accountable the institutions which

affect them". Women in India do not have equal access to autonomy, social freedom, mobility to outside the home, etc. than men. According to Swami Vivekananda, "There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the situation of women is improved" [Zaveri & Shah, 2016]. The concept of women empowerment was introduced at the International Women Conference at NAROIBI in 1985. In a specific sense, women empowerment refers to enhancing their position in the power structure of the society [Orissa Review, 2006]. Empowerment of women is the prerequisite to transform a developing country into a developed country. Empowerment of women is essentially the process of upliftment of economic, social and political status of women, the traditionally underprivileged ones, in the society. Women Empowerment means the full control over intelligent assets, material resources, and even over their philosophies [Zaveri and Shah, 2016].

At the social Summit in Copenhagen in 1993 and the International Conference on Population and Development in Cairo 1994, Governments committed themselves to the empowerment of women [2nd International Conference, IETE, 2018]. As per the United National Development Fund for Women (UNIFEM), the term women's empowerment means [Mir & Tiwari, 2017]: a) Acquiring knowledge and understanding of gender relations and their ways of change, b) Developing a sense of self-worth and right to control one's life, c) Gaining the ability to generate choices, and d) Developing the ability to organize and influence the direction of social change. There are six ways of women empowerment [Nandhini, 2017], such as Individual Women Rights, Social Women Empowerment, Educational Women Empowerment, Economic and Professional Women Empowerment, Legal Women Empowerment and Political Women Empowerment.

Educational attainment and economic participation are the key constituents in ensuring the empowerment of women. The principle of gender equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution in its preamble, fundamental rights, fundamental duties and directive principles [Orissa Review, 2006]. Empowering women enhances their ability to influence changes and to create a better society. The Women rights are the means by which a dignified living is ensured thereby safeguarding her privileges. Empowerment of women could only be achieved by adopting definite social and economic policies with a view of total development of women and to make them realize that they have the potential to be strong human beings. Women have proved themselves as equals in many professions as well as proved themselves even better suited than men in some. Education has given women enlightenment and a vision. Empowerment is an active and multidimensional process which enables women to realize their full identity and powers in all sphere of life [Paachaiyappan, 2014].

Women have realized that they are not mere puppets in the society but a pillar without which the foundation of society is incomplete. Women Empowerment is most vital system to strengthen the future of women in India. It is a systematic approach which needs to develop more seriously in India. The Government of India came up in the new

millennium by declaring the year 2001 as Women's Empowerment Year to focus on a vision, where women are equal partners like men. Empowerment would become more relevant if women are educated, better informed and can take rational decisions by overcoming challenges of equality. Very few numbers of women have been able to establish their potentialities, so everyone should be very much careful for promoting the statuses. India should become a developed nation only if women contribute to the best of her capacity and ability which is possible when they are properly educated and empowered [Singh, 2016].

OBJECTIVES

This study aims to explore the following objectives:

- i) To know the status of Women Education
- ii) To analyze the problems facing Indian women
- iii) To know the justification of Education for Women Empowerment
- iv) To know the Constitutional and Legal Provisions for Women
- v) To know the Governmental Initiatives for Women Empowerment
- vi) To offer useful suggestions on the basis of findings

METHODS OF STUDY

The investigators have presented the study through theoretical basis. The study is based on the secondary data sources. The necessary information's related to women have been collected from various books, journals, magazines, published & unpublished research articles and also from internet sources.

Status of Women Education

Education helps women not only for gaining knowledge but also they can transform their knowledge into application mode through skill development and vocational training. Amartya Sen makes a compelling case for the nation that societies need to see women less as passive recipients of help, and more as dynamic promoters of social transformation, suggesting that the education, employment and ownership rights of women have a powerful influence on their ability to control their environment and contribute to economic development [Sen, 1999]. As the Indian society is very much conservative in nature, the women education has been always neglected from pre-independence to post-independence.

Table 1: Literacy Rate of India

Year	Persons (%)	Male (%)	Female (%)	Male/Female (%)
1901	5.3	9.8	0.7	14.00
1911	5.9	10.6	1.1	9.63
1921	7.2	12.2	1.8	6.77
1931	9.5	15.6	2.9	5.37
1941	16.1	24.9	7.3	3.41
1951	16.7	24.9	7.3	3.41
1961	24.0	34.4	13.0	2.64
1971	29.5	39.5	18.7	2.11
1981	36.2	46.9	24.8	1.89
1991	52.1	63.9	39.2	1.63
2001	65.38	76.0	54.0	1.40
2011	74.04	82.14	65.46	1.25

Source: Census of India Report (2011)

Fig. 1: Census Year wise plot of Male and Female literacy rate

Source: Census of India Report (2011)

Fig. 2: Census Year wise plot of Male and Female literacy rate ratio

Source: Census of India Report (2011)

Table-1 represents the literacy rate (%) of Indian male and female since 2001 to 2011. In the year 1901, the female literacy rate was 0.7 % but the male literacy rate was 9.8 %, indicating fourteen (14) time higher for male literacy than female. During pre-independence period (1901-1941) the female literacy rate has raised from 0.7 % to 7.3 % while the literacy rate of male has risen from 9.8% to 24.9%. During post independence period (1951-2001), the female literacy rate has raised from 7.3% to 54.0 % which is more than seven (7) times, while the male literacy rate has raised from 24.9 % to 76.0 % which is almost three (3) times. During the period 1981-2001, the female literacy rate has increased at a faster rate than male literacy rate. After 2001, Government has implemented various policies and educational opportunities for Indian women but still there is a gap between male and female literacy rate. In 2011, the educated persons were 74.04 % of which female was 65.46 % and male was 82.14 %. From the Figure-1, it is evident that according to census report year male and female literacy rate has gradually increases.

The ratio of Male and Female literacy rate has also been tabulated in Table-1. In the year 1901, the ratio index was 14.00 whereas in the year 2011 the ratio index has decreased to 1.25, indicating female literacy rate has increased gradually from pre independence to till 2011. It is also clear from the Table that both male literacy rate and female literacy rate are in increasing manner, but in some years female literacy rate is slightly more than male literacy rate. If we get the recent Census Report (2021), the ratio index is expended to be lower than that of previous years.

From the Figure-1, it is evident that according to census report year (2011) male and female literacy rate has gradually increases. Figure-2 represents the plot of census year against ratio of male and female literacy rate. The nature of the plot is asymptomatic in nature indicating ratio (%) of male and female literacy rate gradually decreases. The ratio of male and female literacy rate according to the census report of 2021 must follow the asymptomatic nature indicating that female literacy rate (%) is in upward direction.

Among the Indian states, Kerala shows highest literacy rate (more than 90%) and Bihar shows the lowest literacy rate (less than 50%). Even after 65 years of independence, women occupy a secondary position in social hierarchy according to census report 2011. Therefore, women's empowerment can't be effected unless we persuade the importance of women's education [Shindu, 2012].

PROBLEMS FACED BY INDIAN WOMEN:

There are various issues and problems which Indian women generally face in the society. Some of the problems are as follows:

Disparity in Education: The level of women education is less than men still in the modern age. Female illiteracy is higher in the rural areas because they are discouraged for higher education like professional and technical education.

Problems Related to Unemployment & Employment: Women are facing more problems in search of in searching their suitable work. They become more prone to the exploitation and harassment in the work places. Intentionally they are given more work and hard tasks by their boss. Sometimes, they have to prove their devotion, seriousness and sincerity towards their work.

Sexual Harassment: It is the form of sexual exploitation of a girl child at home, streets, schools, public places, transports, offices, etc. by the family members, neighbours, friends, bosses or relatives.

Poverty: Currently poverty is the World's greatest threat to international peace. So, poverty should be abolished as a national goal for the development and success of women.

Selective Abortion and Female Infanticide: It is the most common practice for years in India. In this case abortion of female foetus is performed in the mother's womb after the foetal sex determination and sex selective abortion by the medical professionals.

Domestic Violence: It is the abuse or violence against women. It is like endemic and widespread disease affecting almost 70% of Indian women according to the Women and

Child Development Official. This violence is performed by the husband, relatives or other family members.

Dowry & Bride Burning: It is another major problem generally faced by women of low or middle class family during or after the marriage. Parents of boys demand a lot of money from the bride's family to be rich in one time. It causes degradation of women status to a great extent.

Child Marriage: Child marriage or early marriage of the girls by their parents is in major problem and it is highly practiced in India.

Inadequate Nutrition: Insufficient or Inadequate nutrition in the childhood affects women in their later life, especially women belonging to the lower middle class and poor families.

Fear of Separation or Divorce: Indian women who are uneducated or illiterate faces problems related to divorce and desertion by their husbands at any stage of life. They have to live whole life with fear of divorce. In some cases women have to finish their life because of unbearable conditions or situations.

JUSTIFICATION OF EDUCATION FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Today Indian women are missing chances in various fields of employment and are also segregated for being women. The urban elite class women have been benefitted by the

process of women empowerment but the women of rural areas are very much deprived and exploited due to lack of education. Women are deprived of having decision making power, freedom of movement, access to education, access to employment, exposure to media, domestic violence etc.

Although various attempts have been taken by the Government after independence and even during British rule, the women have not been fully empowered. Women contribute just 8% to 10% in the state assemblies and Parliament respectively.

Hence, there is a need of social, political, economical and cultural empowerment of women irrespective of sex, religion, caste, creed and colour simultaneously through proper education for removal of their entrapped condition. Role of education is very much justified through the following points for Women Empowerment of 21st century not only nationally but also internationally.

i) *Education Promotes Economic Empowerment:* Education helps in Women's Economic Empowerment through self dependent. Educated women are able to apply in

different Govt. and Non-Govt jobs and they can compete with men. Economically, Empowered women may be Ideal or role model for all other women in society and produces long term benefit for country. Education prevents women from falling into poverty.

ii) *Education Empowered Women for Next Generation:* Education provides a brief knowledge to women for their next generation. They can take care of their children and family members. The more education the women received, they can share their educative perspective to their children from early age and their motivational level increases. Educated women provide a better starting point for the next generation.

iii) *Education Empowered Women in Health Issues:* Educated women are more health conscious for not only them but also for other family members. Educated women are aware of their children's health and nutrition. Women education reduces the rate of maternal mortality. Education provides women to overcome their depression or other mental health issues.

iv) *Education Empowers Women as First Teacher:* Children spend more time with their mother and other family members during childhood, and educated mother behaves as the first teacher. When women are educated they tend to encourage and advice their children for becoming educated as well.

v) *Education Enhances Women as Decision Maker:* Education provides self confidence to women and they can take decision independently without the male counterpart. Education provides women to act as decision maker not only for her family but also for her society and nation. The higher the level of education for female, the more opportunity for participation in decision making.

vi) *Education Empowers Female Rights:* Education provides female to be conscious and aware about their fundamental rights & duties and powers them in protecting their rights. Proper education helps women to fight against assaults, eve-teasing, harassment, exploitation etc. When educated female lead in Governmental level, then women push for more equitable systems of governance.

vii) *Education Eliminates Malnutrition:* Malnutrition is responsible for global child deaths. Educated women are more likely to ensure that their children receive the best nutrients to prevent from ill health and hygiene practice.

viii) *Education Empowers Women for Social Awareness:* Educated women can fight against all kinds of social evils and make them social awareness. Most of the social evils are occurring against women rights and their dignity decreases in the society. So, education plays a vital role for empowering women through social awareness.

ix) *Education Reduces Terrorism & Extremism:* Female education reduces the extremism and terrorism and increases security. Educated women are involved in society and the economy. Educated women are less likely to support terrorism and militancy than men of same educational level.

x) *Education Empowers Women as Good for Communities:* An educated woman with economic empowerment returns a lot to the community than male counterparts. Education empowers women to pay value for compassion, empathy and community engagement.

xi) *Education Enhances Women in Balancing Sex Ratio:* Educated women can improve and balance the sex ratio and they are capable of controlling population. They can share their views to other women for the development of society.

xii) *Education Encourages Women:* Education encourages women both in rural and urban to take the advantages of various schemes like Operation Black Board, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao, Various Literacy Programmes etc. for their development and enrichment. Educated women can encourage other female to accept all kinds of educational plans and programmes.

IMPORTANT CONSTITUTIONAL & LEGAL PROVISIONS FOR WOMEN

A. Constitutional Provisions

The Constitution not only grants equality to women, but also empowers the State to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favour of women for neutralizing the socio economic status, education, decision making and politically disadvantages faced by them. These are as follows:

(i) Equality before law for women (Article 14)

(ii) The State not to discriminate against any citizen on grounds only of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth or any of them (Article 15 (i))

(iii) The State to make any special provision in favour of women and children (Article 15 (3))

(iv) Equality of opportunity for all citizens in matters relating to employment or appointment to any office under the State (Article 16)

(v) The State to direct its policy towards securing for men and women equally the right to an adequate means of livelihood (Article 39(a)); and equal pay for equal work for both men and women (Article 39(d))

(vi) To promote justice, on a basis of equal opportunity and to provide free legal aid by suitable legislation or scheme or in any other way to ensure that opportunities for securing justice are not denied to any citizen by reason of economic or other disabilities (Article 39 A)

- (vii)** The State to make provision for securing just and humane conditions of work and for maternity relief **(Article 42)**
- (viii)** The State to promote with special care the educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people and to protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation **(Article 46)**
- (ix)** The State to raise the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people **(Article 47)**
- (x)** To promote harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood amongst all the people of India and to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women **(Article 51(A) (e))**
- (xi)** Not less than one-third (including the number of seats reserved for women belonging to the Scheduled Castes (S.C.) and the Scheduled Tribes (S.T.)) of the total number of seats to be filled by direct election in every Panchayat to be reserved for women and such seats to be allotted by rotation to different constituencies in a Panchayat **(Article 243 D(3))**
- (xii)** Not less than one-third of the total number of offices of Chairpersons in the Panchayats at each level to be reserved for women **(Article 243 D(4))**
- (xiii)** Not less than one-third (including the number of seats reserved for women belonging to the Scheduled Castes (S.C.) and the Scheduled Tribes (S.T.)) of the total number of seats to be filled by direct election in every Municipality to be reserved for women and such seats to be allotted by rotation to different constituencies in a Municipality **(Article 243 T(3))**
- (xiv)** Reservation of offices of Chairpersons in Municipalities for the Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes and women in such manner as the legislature of a State may by provision of law **(Article 243 T(4))**

B. Legal Provisions:

Women may be victims of any of the crimes such as 'Murder', 'Robbery', 'Cheating' etc, and it is known as 'Crime against Women'. These are broadly classified under two categories.

(a) *The Crimes Identified Under the Indian Penal Code (IPC)*

- (i) Rape (Sec. 376 IPC)**
- (ii) Kidnapping & Abduction for different purposes (Sec. 363-373)**
- (iii) Homicide for Dowry, Dowry Deaths or their attempts (Sec. 302/304-B IPC)**
- (iv) Torture, both mental and physical (Sec. 498-A IPC)**

- (v) Molestation (**Sec. 354 IPC**)
- (vi) Sexual Harassment (**Sec. 509 IPC**)
- (vii) Importation of girls (up to 21 years of age)

(b) *The Crimes Identified under the Special Laws (SLL)*

- (i) The Employees State Insurance Act, (1948)
- (ii) The Plantation Labour Act, (1951)
- (iii) The Family Courts Act, (1954)
- (iv) The Special Marriage Act, (1954)
- (v) The Hindu Marriage Act, (1955)
- (vi) The Hindu Succession Act, (1956) with amendment in (2005)
- (vii) Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, (1956)
- (viii) The Maternity Benefit Act, (1961) (Amended in (1995))
- (ix) Dowry Prohibition Act, (1961)
- (x) The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, (1971)
- (xi) The Contract Labour (Regulation and Abolition) Act, (1976)
- (xii) The Equal Remuneration Act, (1976)
- (xiii) The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, (2006)
- (xiv) The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, (1983)
- (xv) The Factories (Amendment) Act, (1986)
- (xvi) Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, (1986)
- (xvii) Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, (1987)
- (xviii) The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, (2005)

GOVERNMENTAL INITIATIVES FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Government took initiatives in four (4) ways for women empowerment and those are as follows:

- (i) ***National Commission for Women:*** In January 1992, the Government set-up this statutory body with a specific mandate to study and monitor all matters relating to the constitutional and legal safeguards provided for women, review the existing legislation to suggest amendments wherever necessary, etc.

(ii) *Reservation for Women in Local Self-Government:* The 73rd Constitutional Amendment Acts passed in 1992 by Parliament ensure one-third of the total seats for women in all elected offices in local bodies whether in rural areas or urban areas.

(iii) *The National Plan of Action for the Girl Child (1991-2000):* The plan of Action is to ensure survival, protection and development of the girl child with the ultimate objective of building up a better future for the girl child.

(iv) *National Policy for the Empowerment of Women, 2001:* The Department of Women & Child Development in the Ministry of Human Resource Development has prepared a “*National Policy for the Empowerment of Women*” in the year 2001. The goal of this policy is to bring about the advancement, development and empowerment of women.

SUGGESTIONS FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH EDUCATION

Education plays a vital role for women empowerment. The picture of female education in the society is not up to the mark. When an woman is empowered, whole family is empowered and thus, the society is also empowered. Education for the women has to pay a greater care and special attention. All though there are constitutional & legal provisions, Governmental initiatives for women empowerment but the problems are still in vogue. The suggestive measures are as follows:

- i) Awareness for women education is very much essential. For this print media, press media, social media etc. should have to play a vital role for broadcasting, telecasting and circulating the effective benefit of women education for their empowerment in society.
- ii) The level of confidence within female have to be raised to some extent to fight for their rights.
- iii) Have to change the approaches towards women based sex discrimination.
- iv) Encourage the women for actively participation in social and political issues.
- v) To develop the feelings of self dependence among women.
- vi) Encourage the women to participate in income generating activities for their self dependent.
- vii) Removal of gender based inequality.
- viii) Child bearing at young ages should be prevented by preventing and protesting early marriages.

- ix) Motivate all the female of rural areas and provide them training programme to foster or nurture their creativity.
- x) Arrangement of various types of training, workshop and courses for grooming of female to enhance their self esteem, self respect, self reliance and self confidence.
- xi) Peoples mentality for ignoring and neglecting women should have to change. Women talent should be emphasised on employment.
- xii) Any kind of discrimination, priority and biasness in employment should be eliminated.
- xiii) There should not exist any kind of wage difference between men and women in Government, Non-government and Private organisations.
- xiv) For working women, safety and support system should be up to the mark in the workplace.
- xv) If any woman faces any kind of problem and goes to depressed mood, there should be provision for psychological counselling.
- xvi) Use of computer, internet and ICT tools should be increased for women education.
- xvii) Women should be motivated towards higher education and engaged in research oriented activities.
- xviii) Large number of night school, integrated school, satellite school etc. should be set up in remote areas for empowering women.
- xix) Parents, those who think that education for their daughter is extra burden and misuse of money, their mentality have to changed.
- xx) Government should provide various schemes for women in their education like free schooling, mid-day meal, dresses, hostel facility, scholarships, train and bus travelling concession etc.

CONCLUSION

India's journey for women empowerment and gender equality started when it became a sovereign state in 1947. Investment for education to empower women indicates a high return investment for socio economic development of a society as well as for the nation. Education reduces inequality and raises the status of women in her family as well as in society and nation.

Top priority should be given in our developmental plans for improving female literacy and creating skills and capability among women for enabling them to stand on their own feet. Education motivates, guides and trains in every level for improving and enhancing their qualities, potentialities and capabilities. The first and foremost priority should be given to the education of women, which is the grass root problem. Women should be empowered in both qualitatively and quantitatively through formal, non-formal and informal approaches.

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